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Traces of Guanyin

In Search of Untold Stories and Practices in Museums

觀音的蹤跡

探尋博物館中不為人知的故事與習俗

URL: <https://tracesofguanyin.eu/>

Curatorial Concept

策展理念

Museum artefacts are seldom in the shape they were before entering museum premises: they are treated with preservative substances to arrest their material decay, restored, and displayed under specific temperature and light conditions. In the past, they were even fragmented at the moment of their collection and reassembled, as in the case of the [Pergamon Altar](#) in Berlin. Asian religious statues, especially those collected in the 19th and 20th centuries, experienced several transformations. From being guests of honour on shrines, once they were collected for museum galleries or storage rooms, they were beheaded, mutilated, fragmented, hollowed. They were no longer sacred icons but complied with the criteria of the art market, aesthetic tastes, erudite knowledge, and societal norms of the audience, other than their worshippers. As shown by art historians, mutilating religious statues could increase the art market's profits derived from the multiplication of fragments to sell and responded to an antiquarian taste towards ruins and

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archaeological remains. These mutilations are seldom problematised in the museum narratives provided in galleries and catalogue entries, and in certain cases, they become appealing aesthetic features. For instance, Buddha heads are such potent symbols of Buddhist art that their reproductions as pleasing and mystical furniture decorations can be found everywhere, from coffee shops to yoga training rooms, without realising that their presence in museums signals past violent lootings or destructions [Fig. 1: [Head of Buddha](#), mid 6th century, Shandong or Hebei provinces, MET Asian collection, not on view, OA photo downloaded from the MET website].

進入博物館收藏的文物，鮮少能保持其進館前的原貌：它們經過防腐處理以減緩材質老化，接受修復，並在特定的溫度與光線條件下展出。過去，文物甚至在採集時被拆解，之後再重組，如：柏林的佩加蒙祭壇便是典型例子。亞洲宗教神像，尤其是於19、20世紀被蒐藏的神像，也經歷了多重轉變。它們曾是神龕上的貴賓，但一旦進入博物館展廳或儲藏室，便可能遭到斬首、毀損、拆解或挖空。此時，它們不再是神聖的信仰象徵，而是轉化為遵循藝術市場規則、美學品味、學術知識與觀眾社會規範的物件，而非原本信徒的崇拜對象。藝術史學家指出，毀損神像並販售碎片，不僅增加藝術市場的獲利，也迎合古董收藏者對遺跡與考古文物的審美偏好。然而，在博物館展廳的敘事與目錄中，這些毀損的神像鮮少被討論；在某些情況下，它們甚至被視為具有吸引力的美學特徵。例如，佛陀頭像視為佛教藝術的重要象徵，從咖啡館到瑜伽教室，隨處都能找到這樣令人賞心悅目且帶有神秘感的複製品為裝飾，人們卻往往沒有意識到，它們在博物館中的存在，也反映了過去的暴力掠奪或破壞。[圖 1：佛陀頭像，公元 6 世紀中期，山東或河北省，紐約大都會藝術博物館亞洲收藏，未展出，OA 照片下載自 MET 網站]

“Traces of Guanyin” prompts the audience to pay closer attention to the signs of decay on statues in museums and to acknowledge them as historical traces of troubled pasts.

This curatorial project reflects on the potential of material traces in accounting for historical and archival silences within museum collections. Material traces of past interventions on religious artefacts stir in us hypotheses about what could have happened, as well as emotions such as uncanniness and grief. “Traces of Guanyin” mobilises these fantasies that emerge from our interaction with past traces and fill the voids of museum narratives. If fantasies and counternarratives resulting from our interaction with traces cannot completely unravel the historical vicissitudes that occurred, they can allow us to imagine possible scenarios that have happened and future trajectories for these museum artefacts. Traces are, therefore, both material

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signs and narrative trajectories that researchers, curators, and audiences follow to make sense of museum collections.

[Fig. 2 The hollowed Buddha from the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography. Photo by Valentina Gamberi, Courtesy of the Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography, Parma, Inventory number cna0680. Figure 3: The hollowed Guanyin collected by the Evangelical Pastor and Sinologist Heinrich Hackmann and now stored at the Religionskundlichesammlung Museum, Philipps-University Marburg. Photo by Heike Luu, Copyright Religionskundlichesammlung, Inventory number Nt 058].

本展覽《觀音的蹤跡》將引導觀眾更加關注博物館中雕像上歲月的痕跡，並將其視為歷史上動盪過往的印記。本次策展計畫探討了如何透過物理上的痕跡揭示博物館藏品中，那些被忽略或沉默的歷史。這些過往遺留在宗教文物上的痕跡，不僅引發我們對歷史事件的推測，也喚起了如詭異與哀傷等複雜的情緒。《觀音的蹤跡》觸動了我們與歷史痕跡互動時所浮現的想像，這些想像填補了博物館敘事中的缺縫。儘管我們擁有的這些想像與反敘事，無法完全解開歷史中曾發生的變遷，我們仍能去構想這些文物過往以及未來的軌跡。因此，這些痕跡，既是物質性的符號，也是敘事性的軌跡；引導研究者、策展人與觀眾在其中追索，以理解博物館的藏品。[圖2 中國藝術與民族誌博物館藏品中的空心佛像。攝影：Valentina Gamberi，帕爾馬中國藝術與民族誌博物館惠允，收藏號 cna0680。圖3：空心觀音，由福音派牧師兼漢學家 Heinrich Hackmann 收藏，現藏於馬爾堡菲利普斯大學宗教收藏博物館。攝影：Heike Luu，版權所有宗教收藏博物館，藏品編號 Nt 058。]

This curatorial project focuses on two Chinese folk religious statues that present hollows in their backs: a Buddha collected by Xaverian missionaries for their Museum of Chinese Art and Ethnography in Parma, and a Guanyin, donated by the Evangelical Pastor and Sinologist Heinrich Hackmann (1864-1935) to the Religionskundlichesammlung of Philipps-University Marburg. In Chinese folk religion—a syncretism of Daoism, Confucianism, and Buddhism practised by the Han and Hakka ethnicities in China, Taiwan, and other areas in Southeast and East Asia—god statues must be spiritually reinforced by inserting sacred substances into a cavity on their backs. Unsealing the latter is therefore a sign of deconsecration. “Traces of Guanyin” narrates the journey undertaken by the anthropologist Valentina Gamberi to understand how and by whom the two statues were unsealed. In her archival and ethnographic experience, Valentina could not provide clear answers: the statues could have been unsealed either by their previous owners or the collectors. Her

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ethnographic research on deconsecration rituals in Taiwan revealed that the practice of removing the sacred substances from is still observed among Taiwanese collectors today.

本策展計畫聚焦於兩尊背部呈現中空結構的中國民間宗教神像：其一為一尊佛像，由沙勿略會（Xaverian）傳教士收藏，現藏於義大利帕瑪的「中國藝術與民族學博物館」；其二為一尊觀音像，由福音派牧師兼漢學家海因里希·哈克曼（Heinrich Hackmann, 1864–1935）捐贈予德國馬堡菲利普斯大學（Philipps-Universität Marburg）的宗教學收藏館（Religionskundlichesammlung）。在華人民間宗教中——此一融合道教、儒家與佛教的信仰體系，廣泛流行於中國、臺灣，以及東南亞與東亞其他地區的漢族與客家社群——神像必須透過將寶置入其背部的內部空腔中，方能完成開光儀式。因此，將神像退寶，亦可被視為一種完成退神（deconsecration）儀式的明確標誌。《觀音的蹤跡》（Traces of Guanyin）敘述了人類學家夏芸庭（Valentina Gamberi）為理解這兩尊神像如何、以及由誰進行退寶而展開的研究歷程。然而，透過其檔案研究與民族誌調查，夏芸庭並未能獲得確切結論：這兩尊空心神像，可能是在進入收藏體系之前由原持有者退寶，也可能是在被收藏之後由收藏者將神像退寶。她於臺灣進行的民族誌研究顯示，至今在部分臺灣收藏者之間，仍可觀察到一種持續存在的實踐——即在神像進入收藏或展示狀態之前，移除其內部的寶，作為退神的儀式的其中一個環節。

By connecting past and present deconsecration practices in Europe and Asia, “Traces of Guanyin” presents a multilayered and multivocal narrative. Unsealing the statues’ hollows is ambiguous: it could reflect local knowledge for spiritually protecting collectors and previous owners from bad luck, but it could also be part of a process of religious conversion and, therefore, iconoclasm. Hollows thus reflect both the local agency and the violence of collectors. By exploring contemporary deconsecration rituals in Taiwan and their inherently controversial and taboo nature, the exhibition highlights the importance of negotiating local, conflicting views on the treatment of sacred artefacts. It also acknowledges that collecting these objects is inherently problematic. At the same time, “Traces of Guanyin” shows that ethnographic accounts alone cannot fully explain discarded matter. Instead, the exhibition traces multiple journeys, voices, and perspectives reverberating through hollowed god statues. It decenters the ethnographer by bringing in other voices and experiences from fieldwork—Valentina’s friend, Chang Yuhua, and the contemporary artist Peng Hung-Chih—and reveals her awkwardness in researching sensitive topics.

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透過連結歐洲與亞洲過去與當代的退神儀式的實踐，《觀音的蹤跡》(Traces of Guanyin) 建構出一個多層次且多聲部的敘事結構。對將神像退保的行為本身具有高度的曖昧性：它既可能反映一種在地知識，意在於從靈性層面保護收藏者與前任持有者免於厄運；同時，也可能構成宗教轉換過程的一環，因而帶有聖像破壞 (iconoclasm) 的意涵。因此，空心神像同時折射出在地行動者的能動性，以及收藏行為所隱含的暴力。藉由探討當代臺灣的退神儀式及其內在所具有的爭議性與禁忌性，本展覽凸顯了在處理神聖物件時，協商彼此衝突且在地化觀點的重要性，並同時承認對此類物件的收藏行為本身即具有問題性。然而，《觀音的蹤跡》亦指出，僅憑民族誌敘述並不足以充分解釋那些被棄置的物質。展覽因此追溯多重行動軌跡、聲音與觀點，這些經驗在空心神像之中相互迴盪。透過引入田野工作中其他聲音與經驗——包括夏芸庭的友人張玉華 (Yuhua Chang)，以及當代藝術家彭弘智 (Hung-Chih Peng) ——本展覽刻意去中心化民族誌研究者的視角，並揭示研究者在面對敏感議題時所經歷的遲疑、不安與侷促。

References

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